

Molecular Genotyping of Knockdown Resistance Mutation (L995F) and Profiling Pyrethroids Resistance in *Anopheles gambiae*

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Abstract

Mosquitos' resistance to pyrethroids insecticides pose a serious threat to the control of malaria and other diseases it transmits. To genotype the resistance mutation and determine the pyrethroids resistance profile in *Anopheles gambiae* population, adult mosquito bioassay and genotyping of kdr mutation (L995F) were carried out on sampled mosquitoes from two localities (Igala quarters and Tudun wada) in Gusau, Zamfara State, Nigeria. Four replicates of 20 adult *A. Gambiae* were exposed to 0.75% Permethrin and 0.05% Deltamethrin using the World Health Organisation (WHO) adult bioassay method. Resistant and Susceptible samples were then genotyped for the voltage-gated sodium channel (VGSC) gene mutation using allele-specific polymerase chain reaction (AS-PCR). The range of percentage mortalities in all the treatments were from 78.75 – 85% which clearly indicated resistance was confirmed. Genotyping of the L995F mutation revealed high allelic frequency of 87.5% and 70% in resistant phenotype from Igala quarters and Tudun wada respectively. Between the resistant and susceptible phenotypes from each location, there was no discernible correlation in the 995F allele frequency (Fisher's exact test, $p = 1.00$). According to the study's findings, the resistant phenotype of *A. gambiae* exhibited pyrethroids resistance with a high allelic frequency. Continuous profiling of resistance status and genotyping of associated mutation will help in knowing the extent of the mutation developed to avoid the development of super resistant mutation and its transgression.

Keywords: Genotyping, Knockdown Resistance (kdr), Mutation, Mutant allele, Resistant, Susceptible, VGSC gene.

1.0 Introduction

Pyrethroids are currently the most widely used insecticides to manage crop pests and other insects that are crucial to public health, like mosquitoes [1]. However, according to reports from West and East Africa, pyrethroid insecticide-resistant *Anopheles* mosquitoes exist [2]. Between 2010 and 2020, pyrethroid resistance was reported in over 38 countries, with varied degrees of intensity. Consequently,

this has become a noteworthy public health issue [1, 3].

Pyrethroids disrupt normal functioning of nerves of insect by changing kinetic of the voltage-sensitive sodium channels which mediate transitory increase in the sodium penetrability of nerve membrane during the rising phase of nerve action potential [4]. The pyrethroids target the central nervous system, their principal mechanism of action involves interacting with voltage-gated sodium channels (VGSCs) in

neurons. The interaction results in depolarization due to the extended input of sodium ions [5]. Extended depolarization is the cause of recurrent neuronal activity, which can be fatal and cause hyperexcitation [5]. It has also been discovered that certain pyrethroids suppress ATPase activity [6]. Additionally, research has revealed that certain pyrethroids interact with the aminobutyric acid receptor; typically, type II pyrethroids exhibit this more frequently [6].

Because of the numerous selection pressures placed on mosquito populations by human activity, mosquitoes have developed a rapid adaptive response known as insecticide resistance [5]. Mosquitoes have a variety of inherited resistance strategies that involve behavioral and physiological alterations [7]. Over expression of a number of enzyme families, including glutathione-S-transferases, esterases, and cytochromes P450, can lead to pyrethroids resistance [8]. Furthermore, mutations in structural genes that decrease the insecticide's binding such as *ace-1R* (ace tylocholinesterase), *rdl* (resistant to dieldrin), *super-kdr* (enhanced knockdown resistance), and *kdr* (knockdown resistant), cause mosquitoes to become insensitive to certain sites [7]. Another process that is now thought to be a mosquito resistance mechanism is the decreased uptake of insecticides [8]. Moreover, behavioral modifications in response to insecticides exposure that enable mosquitoes to elude control measures are also regarded as insecticide resistance mechanisms [9]. The identification of unique numerous up-regulated gene families encoding for insecticide binding proteins has been made possible by a meta-analysis technique applied to transcriptome data from populations of *A. gambiae* resistant to the commonly used pyrethroid insecticides. Among these are α -crystallins and hexamerins, which decrease mosquito mortality following treatment and are up-regulated in response to deltamethrin exposure [9]. A whole genome microarray approach, as reported by Isaacs [10], indicates that *A. gambiae* insecticides resistance may be closely associated with over expression of genes encoding salivary gland proteins. The transfer of hydrophobic compounds has been associated with the chemosensory protein family, which includes the mosquito sensory appendage protein (SAP2), a recently discovered mechanism [11].

Pyrethroid resistance is caused by a main mechanism known as knockdown resistance (*kdr*) mutation, which acts by altering the channel's action potential and decreasing the receptors' sensitivity (binding capacity) to the insecticides [12]. This resistance mechanism has a number of effects; it either wipes out or lessens the knockout effect, as well as the irritating and repellent effects. The *kdr* gene, also known as the voltage gated sodium channels (VGSCs) gene, is impacted by the mutations [12, 13]. The target-site insensitivity of *A. gambiae* is related with two dissimilar mutations in the transmembrane segment 6 of domain II (DIIS6) of para type sodium channel at position 995. The results of the mutations include leucine (TTA) to phenylalanine (TTT) (L995F) or leucine (TTA) to serine (TCA) (L995S) substitutions [14, 15]. The former mutation, known as *kdr-west*, was shown to be widespread in West Africa [15], whereas the later mutation, known as *kdr-east*, was first identified in East Africa [3]. Notwithstanding, studies have indicated that the 995F allele is located in East Africa [16] and West Africa [17]. These results imply that the regional distribution of the two mutations is not what was previously stated. In *A. gambiae*, the African malaria vector, these two-point mutations confer resistance against DDT and pyrethroid insecticides [18]. Both the molecular form of *A. gambiae* (*A. coluzzii*) and S molecular form of *A. gambiae* (*A. gambiae* s. s.) have been found to carry the L995F mutation. However, according to Souza [5], the L995S was only seen in the M-form. Both types of mutations have been linked to pyrethroid resistance; yet, in *A. coluzzii*, a high frequency of the 995F *kdr* allele has been strongly linked to resistance to lambda-cyhalothrin [19].

A deeper understanding of the genetic makeup of vector populations in environments where insecticides are used extensively in conjunction with other control measures can be gained by tracking the development of resistance [20]. Significant logistical obstacles arise while trying to effectively control the malarial vector amidst the emergence of insecticides resistance. Moreover, there are useful ramifications for the creation of gene-drive mosquito control systems for large levels of natural variability [21].

Moreover, by editing a particular gene to give a phenotype, like female sterility using CRISPR-Cas9 gene drives, have the potential to lower

mosquito populations and thereby lessen the spread of disease. The effectiveness of gene drives in the field, however, may be compromised by naturally occurring polymorphisms in the roughly 21 base pair (bp) Cas9 target location, which could impede target recognition [21, 22].

Mosquitoes-borne diseases are preventable, which heavily relied on the use of chemical insecticides, notably pyrethroids. Whereas, the development of mutation in resistance to these insecticides in mosquito vector is a dynamic phenomenon in time and space [18]. Hence, a better understanding of the molecular, ecological and evolutionary processes driving insecticides resistance and spread of associated mutation in the mosquito vector is essential to maximize the active lifespan of existing insecticides and to accelerate the development of new strategies and tools for vector control [17]. Therefore, knowing the resistance profile and the genotypes of both the resistant and susceptible mosquitoes will guide in understanding how transgression of genes often occur among the mosquitoes. The objective is to identify the contribution of knockdown resistance (kdr) mutation L995F in voltage-gated sodium channel and profile resistance to the pyrethroid insecticides.

2.0 Materials and Methods

2.1 Study Area

Gusau is geographically located on latitude (12.1628° N) and longitude (6.6745° E) and serves as the capital of Zamfara state in northwestern Nigeria. The state shares boundaries with Sokoto, Kebbi, Niger, Kaduna, Katsina states and Niger republic. Gusau town has an area of 3,364 km² and an estimated population of 383,162 as at 2006 census. Gusau has a tropical continental climate type, characterized by distinct wet (April – October) and dry (November – March) seasons with an average annual temperature of 30.22°C (86.4°F) [39].

2.2 Collection and Rearing of Mosquitoes

Mosquito larvae and pupae were collected directly from the breeding site at two sampling sites (Igal quarters and Tudun Wada) by scooping-up with an entomological ladle and

pipetting with Pasteur [23]. In September, 2023. The obtained samples were sorted and kept apart from other detritus and predators using plastic trays at a density of roughly 100/L of deionized water. Pupae were pipetted into tiny paper cups and placed in mosquito rearing cages, while larvae were given a diet consisting of ground dog biscuits, liver of beef, powdered-milk, and brewer's yeast in 2:1:1:1 ratio. Ten percent sucrose was sucked into cotton wool, and placed on the cage netting to feed the adult mosquitoes that had emerged. Conventional insect conditions were upheld, with temperature 27±2°C, a relative humidity (RH) of 75±10%, and a light dark cycle of 12:12 hours [23, 24].

2.3 Morphological Identification

The Stereo Zoom microscope 7X-45X Trinocular XTL was used to identify *Anopheles* mosquitoes through microscopical identification using morphological criteria [25, 26]. Pictorial keys were also used in this process. The dark spot in the upper margins of wings, the palpis being as long as the proboscis, the wings' blocks of black and white scales, the legs' speckles, the third preapical dark area on vein 1 with a pale of interruption, and the Tersi 1 to 4 with noticeable pale of bands were the main features used for identification [25].

2.4 DNA Extraction

Genomic DNA was extracted using a procedure that has been developed [27, 28]. 1.6 ml of 5M NaCl, 5.48 g sucrose, 1.57 g Tris, 10.16 EDTA ml 0.5M, 2.5 ml SDS20%, and distilled sterile and deionized water were used to generate the Livak grinding buffer. The volume of solution was then increased to 100 ml. After sterilizing and filtering, the solution was sub-aliquoted and kept at -20°C. A single mosquito was homogenized in 1.5 mL of preheated Livak grinding buffer using operated battery mortar and pestle (SIGMA), and the homogenate was then immediately incubated at 65 °C for 30 minutes. Following the incubation period, the condensation was collected using a quick microcentrifuge, and 14 µL of potassium acetate (8 M) was added to reach a 1M final concentration of. After pulsating vortexing the samples, they were incubated on ice for almost half an hour. After centrifuging the tubes for 20 minutes at 4 °C at 15,000 rpm, the supernatant

was carefully transferred to a fresh 1.5 mL Eppendorf tube. After adding 200µL of ethanol 100%, the mixture was centrifuged once more for 15 minutes at 4 °C and 15,000 rpm. The pellets were then rinsed with 100µL of 70% ice-cold ethanol, allowed to air dry approximately an hour and then again suspended in 100µL distilled water. The supernatant was disposed of at this point. Finally, the pellets (DNA) were incubated for 10 minutes at 65 °C [28, 29].

2.5 Molecular Identification of Mosquitoes

Intergenic sequence (IGS) sections of ribosomal DNA (rDNA) were amplified using the primers IGS441 Forward (5'-TGG TCT GGG GAC CAC GTC GAC ACA GG-3') and IGS783 Reverse (5'-CGT TTC TCA CAT CAA GACAAT CAA GTC-3') [34, 35]. KAPA Taq DNA polymerase was used in the PCR reaction. 1µL of genomic DNA, 1.5µL of 10 Taq A Buffer, about 0.4M (0.51µL) of forward and reverse primer, 1.25mM of MgCl₂, 0.25mM of dNTP mixes, and 0.12µL of Taq DNA polymerase in ddH₂O made up the reaction mix. The conditions for amplification were as follows: Denaturation at 95 °C for 5 minutes followed by 35 cycles of final denaturation at 95 °C for 30 seconds, annealing at 51 °C for 40 seconds, extension at 72 °C for 60 seconds and final extension at 72 °C for 10 minutes. One unit of Msel and one unit of 1× of buffer 2 (New England Biolabs Beverly, MA) are added to the PCR following amplification. The PCR amplicons were separated in 1.5 % agarose gel electrophoresis pre-stained with ethidium bromide for 35 minutes at 110 volts.

2.6 Pyrethroids Susceptibility Test (Percentage Mortality)

The protocol provided by WHO [24], was used to carry out the adult bioassays. Four replicates of twenty adult *A. gambiae* were subjected for sixty minutes to filter paper saturated with 0.75% Permethrin and 0.05% Deltamethrin. Mortalities were recorded 24hrs post-exposure to the pyrethroids. The dead mosquitoes were stored in silica gel (fisher scientific, UK) to avoid desiccation while some of the survivors were kept at -20°C for additional analysis. Result of the bioassay was interpreted as suggested by WHO as follows; confirmed resistance (mortality less than 90%); possible resistance (mortality

between 90%–97%) and susceptible (mortality between 98–100%).

2.7 Investigation and genotyping of Knockdown Resistance (kdr) Mutation

An adaptation of the methods created by [14, 15] was utilized to detect the L995F kdr alleles. The L995F allele (AS-PCR Agd3) was found using primers; Agd1 (5'-atagattccccgaccatg-3'), Agd2 (5'-agacaaggatgatgaacc-3'), Agd3 (5'-aatttcattacttacgaca-3'), and Agd4 (5'-ctgtagtataggaattta-3') (Figure 2.1). One microliter of template DNA, one x PCR Qiagen buffer, MgCl₂ of 0.5 mM, 100 nM of primer each, 200 µM of dNTPs, and one unit of polymerase Taq DNA (Taq PCR core kit Qiagen Hilden, Germany) were used in the 50 µl process for amplification. first denaturation at 94°C for 5 minutes followed by ten cycles of one minute denaturation at 94°C, thirty seconds of annealing at 54°C, and thirty seconds of extension at 72°C. These cycles were then followed by thirty cycles of one minute denaturation by 94°C, thirty seconds of annealing at 47°C, and thirty seconds of extension at 72°C, with a final extension at 72°C lasting for ten minutes. After ethidium bromide staining, the products amplified were examined on a 2% agarose gel and imaged using a Syngene bio-imaging system. By way of dividing the total number of mosquitoes analyzed with the number of individual mosquitoes with a certain genotype, the genotype frequency was determined.

Figure 2.1: Schematic representation of AS-PCR which detects L995F mutation. **Source:** [32]

2.8 Data Analysis

Mortality (Number of dead mosquitoes) between the two sampling locations was compared using T-test with SPSS version 20 software. The allelic frequency relationship between resistant and susceptible phenotypes was checked using Fisher's exact test with SPSS version 20 software. Analysis of WHO tube bioassay results and plots was performed using Microsoft excel 2010.

3.0 Result

3.1 Morphological and Molecular Identification

Adult mosquitoes were identified based on morphological characteristics utilizing pictorial keys as *A. gambiae*. Polymerase chain reaction-based molecular identification method confirmed the mosquito's population composed of *A. gambiae* s. (the S molecular form of *A. gambiae*) and *A. coluzzii* (the M molecular form of *A. gambiae*). The PCR product of mosquitoes when electrophoresed had band size of 288 bp and 181 bp (Plate 3.1).

Plate 3.1: Gel Electrophoresis of PCR products of *A. Gambiae* identification. **Lane 1:** 1kb ladder, **lane 2:** negative control, **lane 3 & 4:** band indicating *A. gambiae* s. s. (288 bp) and *A. coluzzii* (181 bp)

3.2 Pyrethroids Susceptibility Test (Percentage Mortality)

In Igala quarters and Tudun wada, the observed percentage mortality in all the adult bioassays are below 90% (<90%). In all the treatments, the percentage mortality ranged between 78.75% and 85%. The percentage mortality of *A. Gambiae* at Tudun wada was 80% for Permethrin and 85% for Deltamethrin while relatively low percentage mortality was recorded at Igala quarters with Permethrin (78.75%) and Deltamethrin (81.25%) (Figure 3.1). Percentage mortality of mosquitoes at Tudun wada was slightly higher than that of Igala quarters when mosquitoes were exposed to both Permethrin ($p = 0.868$, $t = 0.174$, $df = 6$) and Deltamethrin ($p = 0.524$, $t = 0.676$, $df = 6$) (Table 3.1).

3.3 Knockdown Resistance Mutation (L995F) Genotypes

A total of 133 mosquitoes from both locations were selected at random and genotyped. Forty two of the mosquitoes were from resistant (alive) phenotype while ninety one were of susceptible (dead) phenotype (Table 3.2). The *kdr* genotypes identified based on characteristics bands were: 293 bp which was common to both susceptible and resistant genotypes, 137 bp associated with susceptible (995L/L) genotypes, 195 bp associated with resistant (995F/F) genotypes and heterozygous (995L/F) genotypes represented by the presence of all three bands indicate (Plate 3.2).

Figure 3.1: Percentage mortality of *A. gambiae* after 24 hours post-exposure to the pyrethroid from Igala quarters and Tudun wada.

Table 3.1: Percentage mortality of *A. gambiae* with corresponding phenotype

Insecticide	Location	Number of Mosquitoes Tested	Number of Dead Mosquitoes (Mortality %)	Number of Mosquitoes (Phenotypic Status)	<i>P</i>
Permethrin	Igala quarters	80	63(78.75)	17(R) 63(S)	0.868
	Tudun wada	80	64(80.00)	16(R) 64(S)	
Deltamethrin	Igala quarters	80	65(81.25)	15(R) 65(S)	0.524
	Tudun wada	80	68(85.00)	12(R) 68(S)	

R = Resistant phenotype; **S** = Susceptible phenotype; **P** = level of significance value.

Plate 3.2: Gel electrophoresis of AS-PCR products to detect *kdr* L995F mutation. **Lane 1:** 100kb ladder, **lane 3 & 4:** homozygous resistant genotype (995F/F), **lane 2 & 6:** heterozygous genotype (995L/F), **lane 5 & 7:** homozygous wild-type (susceptible) genotype (995L/L), **lane 8:** negative control.

3.4 Knockdown Resistance Mutation (L995F) Genotypic and Allelic Frequencies

In Permethrin resistant phenotype, 100% genotypic frequency with 75% homozygous (995F/F) and 25% heterozygous (995L/F) were observed at Igala quarters, while 90% genotypic frequency with 50% homozygous (995F/F) and 40% heterozygous (995L/F) were observed at Tudun wada (Table 3.2).

In Deltamethrin resistant phenotype, 87.5% genotypic frequency with 62.5% homozygous (995F/F) and 25% heterozygous (995L/F) were observed at Igala quarters, while 75% genotypic

frequency with 25% homozygous (995F/F) and 50% heterozygous (995L/F) was observed at Tudun wada was (Table 3.2).

Allelic frequency of 87.5% and 70% at Igala quarters and Tudun wada was recorded respectively in Permethrin resistant phenotype. Also, allelic frequency of 5% and 6.83% at Igala quarters and Tudun wada was recorded respectively in Permethrin susceptible phenotype. There is no significant association of 995F allele frequency between resistant and susceptible phenotypes from each location (Fisher' exact test, $p = 1.00$) (Table 3.2).

Table 3.2: *A. gambiae* genotypic and allelic frequencies

Insecticide	Location	Number of Mosquitoes Genotyped	Genotypes (Frequencies %)			Allele (Frequency %)	Fisher's exact test P ($\alpha = 0.05$)
			995F/F	995L/F	995L/L	995F	
Permethrin	Igala quarters	12(R)	9 (75.00)	3 (25.00)	0 (0.00)	10.5(87.50)	1.00
		20(S)	0 (0.00)	2 (10.00)	18 (90.00)	1(5.00)	
	Tudun wada	10(R)	5 (50.00)	4 (40.00)	1 (10.00)	7(70.00)	1.00
		22(S)	1 (4.55)	1 (4.55)	20 (90.91)	1.5(6.83)	
Deltamethrin	Igala quarters	8(R)	5 (62.50)	2 (25.00)	1 (12.50)	6(75.00)	1.00
		24(S)	0 (0.00)	3 (12.50)	21 (87.50)	1.5(6.25)	
	Tudun wada	12(R)	3 (25.00)	6 (50.00)	3 (25.00)	6(50.00)	1.00
		25(S)	0 (0.00)	0 (0.00)	25 (100.00)	0(0.00)	

R = Resistant phenotype; **S** = Susceptible phenotype; **N** = Total number of mosquitoes with corresponding phenotype; **995F/F** (Homozygous Resistant); **995L/F** (Heterozygous); **995L/L** (Homozygous Susceptible); **995F** (Mutant Allele).

4.0 Discussion

To successfully and effectively direct the use of insecticides in malaria vector control programs, it is necessary to identify the resistant profile of the dominant vector species and possible underlying molecular pathways driving the resistance in the field. This allows for the careful selection of an insecticide based on the type and level of existing resistance.

A. gambiae s. s. and *A. coluzzii* were the members of the *A. gambiae* complex identified in the study area during the rainy season (Period of peak malaria transmission). Ibrahim [18] identified *A. coluzzii* as the primary malaria vector in northern Nigeria, while Akpan [33] discovered *A. gambiae* s. s. inside the *A. gambiae* complex that is spread throughout Zamfara state. In Taraba state, northeastern Nigeria, Lamidi [34] similarly discovered that the prevalent species within the *A. gambiae* complex were *A. coluzzii* and *A. gambiae* s. s. Because of the diurnal temperature range, which makes the species more susceptible

to climatic changes and contributes to their wide spread, these species are especially abundant in these places [33].

The adult bioassay results showed that the tested *A. gambiae* population is resistant to the two pyrethroids (Deltamethrin and Permethrin). The percentage mortality recorded confirmed resistance in the tested population which is in accordance with WHO standard [24]. Local selective pressure from intense use of pyrethroids for indoor residual spraying and long-lasting insecticidal nets maybe the contributory factor for the resistance. Comparatively, from our result, there were generally slight significant mortalities in populations of Tudun wada than Igala quarters. This may be attributed to the economic affordability of insecticides and its use. Previous studies also found resistance to pyrethroids. Example, recent study by Ibrahim and colleagues [18, 19] documented high resistance to pyrethroid with percentage mortalities of 1 - 68% and 52 - 78% in 2019 and 2014 respectively in the northern Nigeria (Jigawa, Kano and Katsina state). Another study from Kano state by

Ononamadu [35] observed high level of resistance to Permethrin (mortality of 43%). Also, a research from Adamawa state (north eastern Nigeria) by Wahedi [36] reported resistance to Deltamethrin (Type II Pyrethroid) with percentage mortality of 78 – 87%.

The resistance identified in the *A. gambiae* population under study was undoubtedly influenced by the high frequency of the L995F kdr mutation that we had seen. In *A. gambiae* wide spread all over Africa, the L995F mutation in the voltage-gated sodium channels (VGSCs), the target site of pyrethroids, is frequently linked to insecticide resistance. Tanzania [37], Benin [20] and Burkina Faso [38] have all documented cases of the mutation.

The genotypic frequency showed that there are more homozygous individuals than heterozygous individuals in the Permethrin resistant phenotype while little disparity was observed in Deltamethrin resistant phenotype. Clearly from our result, homozygous mutants indicated higher chances of survival under Permethrin treatment. Although, equal chances of survival between homozygous and heterozygous mutants under Deltamethrin treatment was indicated. Also, heterozygous mutants were observed in susceptible phenotype (very small percentage). This heterozygosity may result in the removal of susceptible individuals, leaving the first resistant. This could happen via consanguinity and preferential mating, which will only pass on the resistance allele (995F) to their progeny, ensuring the spread of mutation within the population [38]. For improved validation, more research with a bigger sample size is necessary. The limitation of this study is that we did not sequence the VSGC gene to check for novel mutations.

5.0 Conclusion

The presence of the two molecular forms of *A. gambiae* (*A. gambiae* s. s. and *A. coluzzii*) was ascertained in the study area. The pyrethroids susceptibility test of the adult mosquitoes confirmed their resistance to Permethrin and Deltamethrin. The presence of mutation for the resistance was observed by genotyping some of the treated mosquitoes. The genotypic frequency showed that there are more homozygous resistant (995F/F) individuals than heterozygous (995L/F) individuals. These records of the pyrethroids resistance and the high frequency of mutant allele (995F) in *A. gambiae* s. s. and *A. coluzzii* pose a

serious threat to control and management of mosquito vector that may lead to escalated incidences of diseases spread by these vectors. It is paramount to intensify effort in continuous profiling resistance status and genotyping the associated mutation to guide best control measure.

6.0 Recommendation

For control and management of mosquito vector borne diseases, knowing the insecticide resistance status of the vector is critical for a better decision making. A continuous genotyping of the mosquito vector will help in knowing the extent of the mutation developed to avoid development of super resistant mutation and its transgression. Other recommendations may include:

- Deciphering the bionomics of parasite-vector relationship for possible control measures.
- Developing a synergy of information flow between researchers and insecticides producing companies for new trend of resistance and effective insecticides development.
- Use of genetic engineering tools such as CRISPR Cas, Prime editing, TALENs, ZFNs, RNAi etc. to the vector control research programs.

7.0 Reference

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